

**TRADUIRE LA LITTÉRATURE D'ENFANCE ET DE JEUNESSE.
LES CLASSIQUES FRANÇAIS TRADUITS VERS LE ROUMAIN /**

**TRANSLATING CHILDREN'S LITERATURE.
THE FRENCH CLASSICS IN ROMANIAN TRANSLATION**

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Children's Literature is one of the most dynamic and interesting corpus of analysis in Translation Studies. Our research is a contribution to the study of its place in the history of literary translation, with examples from French classics translated into Romanian. The History of Translation into Romanian, a monumental project that is still in progress, will be often cited as a rich resource of data for the 20th century, which is particularly interesting for our study as it is the period of retranslations, where the multimodal dimension of translated texts is enhanced. Issues such as translator's visibility and editorial strategies of modernizing older texts will be included in the study.